

The Ecological Impacts in the Select Novels of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni

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Abstract

The word Eco Criticism was coined in 1978 by William Rueckert. Cheryll Glotfelty, one of the chief originators in the study defines Eco Criticism as, "the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment". Many Indian writers like Raja Rao, R.K.Narayan, Anita Desai, Shashi Deshpande, and Arundhati Roy contributed considerably to eco criticism. Chitra Banerjee uses the diverse basics of nature in the first novel, *The Mistress of Spices*. She makes use of aquatic life as the setting. Indian Spices are entwined in the novel, used by Tilo skilfully to cure and restore to health, the Asian community in Oakland. Nature is presented in the full cycle of creation, preservation and destruction. In the second novel, *The Palace of Illusions* she presents man as self-centred and how he surpasses Nature. *The Palace of Illusions* is a re-reading of the Mahabharata, from an Eco critical standpoint. She censures men's ego and insatiable greed resulted in the destruction of both his kind and nature in the War of Kurukshetra. This present paper aims to study multi-faceted ecological aspects in the myths of India from the perspective of *The Mistress of Spices* and *The Palace of Illusions* by Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni.

Keywords: Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Ecological, Ego Vs. Eco, Existentialism, Exploitation, Myth, Eco criticism, migrant, narrative, relocation, rural, urban, South-Asian American, translation, transnational, women's literature.

Eco Criticism is the study of relation between environment and living organisms in their natural environment and their relationships with that environment. It also concerns man's relationships with his physical environment are mirrored in literature.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is born on July 29, 1956 in Kolkata. She is an Indian-American author, Poet, Novelist, Short Story writer, Children's fiction writer, Book Reviewer, Columnist and the most noted woman writer of Indian Diaspora. Her works deal with the themes of diaspora, gender discriminations, magic realism, fantasy, identity crisis, and ecological influence, etc. *The Mistress of Spices* (1997) is her debut novel which depicts the daily life of immigrants living in California. In the novel, Chitra Banerjee employs a lot of natural elements to make the descriptions more vivid. The whole novel revolves around the relationship of the protagonist with spices. Tilo, the heroine validates the power of sensing spices. Spices are personified to portray their predictable role in the novel. Nature is God's gift to Mankind. It is omniscient and consider as a creator, preserver, protector as well as destroyer. Nature holds

an unsurpassable place in one's life. The Life of human beings is highly interlinked with the environment they live in. As literature scrutinizes human life it has recorded the importance of nature in it.

The Mistress of Spices

Eco-criticism serves as a connection between literature, nature and human beings. In *The Mistress of Spices*, Tilo, the protagonist is an adept in perceiving the secret powers of spices, and dedicates her life to it. Her proficiency helps her in sensing the problems of people. Tilo (Nayan Tara) was born in India, was neglected by her family members. When her mother fails to feed due to fever nature becomes Tilo's mother and feeds her. Tilo becomes closer to nature and interweaves her whole life with varied elements of nature from her birth. She is considered special as she has an innate magical power of predicting the future which solved the problems of the villagers. Nature brings change in her life. As her recognition goes overseas pirates kidnap her and make her the queen of pirates and call her as 'Bhagyavathi', meaning a 'harbinger'. She does not like to be a pirate queen. So, she sends her calling thought over the water and it helps her with a typhoon. She is saved by the serpents of under water and takes her to an unknown world of spices and magic led by the serpents. She is engaged to a mystifying island where she is trained by the First Mother to use spices as healing elements. She gets elected by the First Mother as the spice girl and named as Tilo after sesame, the spice of nourishment which means life-giver, and restorer of health and hope. Tilo's life is highly tangled with nature as she has the unique power of understanding the spices. She discovers herself as a mistress of spices. She acts according to the instruction given by the spices around her. Later, Tilo runs a famous spice bazaar in California. All spices in her shop bow to her command and surrender their magic powers and their properties. Every Indian spice found in her store could interact with her. It serves as a companion to Tilo it has the rights to warn and punish her. As red chilli is a symbol of danger it warns her when she thinks about the American guy, Raven. In order to give importance to spices, Chitra Banerjee has personified the spices. Spices are depicted as an embodiment of the native culture.

The novel *The Mistress of Spices* is divided into fifteen chapters of which, except two, are named after different spices and also presented an astonishing story on spices with a mix of nature. Thus, Nature becomes an essential part in the setting of the novel. It helps her to describe her thoughts majestically. It also helps her in portraying the emotions and the feeling of the narrator and reflects the tradition of the land the spices belong to. The First Mother lives on the island where Tilo lands and spends her time in the mystical island to learn from the old one. From the magical island Tilo is transported through the fire of Shampati (the Eastern Phoenix) to Oakland. Chitra Banerjee uses the fundamentals of nature to outshine the world of nature. The novelist uses similes, metaphors, and adjectives from the nature to bring profundity to her narrations and explanations. Nature is filled with colours and has its own connotation. Chitra Banerjee employs colours to describe definite things. Yellow colour signifies the new-year where green suggests harvest, and red denotes the good fortune of bride. The five elements of nature - the air, water, earth, space, and fire are masterly interwoven in the story. Nature serves as a deciding authority in the novel. Raven, the lover of Tilo is a wealthy alcoholic man. His life is renewed by the guidance of a raven which he sees in a hospital. Raven is instructed to meet Tilo which brings him the joy of life. Maya, the name given by Raven to Tilo, reveals the reality of her thinking over earthly paradise. However, they detain that a new world can be created from the remnants of the flustered world. Thus the nature's cycle comes closely beside with the whole plot from the beginning till the end. From the birth of Nayan Tara alias Tilo as a foreseer, Nature is preserved and re-instituted towards the end of the novel. The powers given to Tilo are taken back and is exploded as she violates the rules of getting emotionally and physically attached to Raven. Towards the end, the devastating earthquake

signifies the Indian philosophy of creation, preservation, and destruction completing the nature's cycle. The earthquake comes to conclude the critical situation of Tilo. The earthquake terminates everything but not her faith. Nature is the great healer of life. It can protect, it can devour, and it can revivify life from the obliteration.

The Palace of Illusions

The second novel *The Palace of Illusions* (2008) is a re-writing of the Indian epic, *Mahabharata*, from an eco-critical perspective. It is half-history, half-myth, and wholly magical which is narrated by Draupadi, the protagonist. An exploration of the narration highlights the novel as an assessment of war and environmental destruction. She reprimands men whose ego and unappeasable greed resulted in the colossal destruction of both his clan and nature in the War of Kurukshetra. In her mythic tale, Divakaruni clearly voices her concerns for nature and criticizes man's anthropocentric attitude. The novel traces Draupadi's life from her birth to her the path of the great departure and presents the entire chain of events that led to the War of Kurukshetra resulting in death of millions and widespread destruction of man and his environment, and thereby marking the end of Dvapara Yuga. This novel gives grave awareness of Nature, its relationship to humankind and the human attitude towards it. The Great War causes mammoth chaos to human civilisation leaving behind rotting corpses, wailing mothers, widowed brides and orphaned children as well as the destruction it caused to nature. The entire story revolves around Man's ego and its consequent war, Divakaruni brings in the attention to nature. War from prehistoric times has bewildered nature and by time its devastation has increased multifariously.

The author recounts how Yudhishthir went into dejection after his victory in Kurushetra. This hostility against man-made damage finds its most irrefutable tone in Vyasa, the author of the epic itself. Divakaruni is also influential of the greed and obnoxious vein in man that destroys, overpowers and exploits nature for his selfish needs and to satisfy his ego. Arjun's act of setting fire to the entire forest in Khandav is an evidence of it. So all-encompassing is the knocking down that scarcely any cries of animals are heard when the Pandavas came to build their kingdom, Indrapastha, in it. Any type of settlement in the backwoods is anthropocentric. By using natural resources according to their whims and fancies, man reduces nature in a hierarchy, as if they survive for humans. This human attitude that reputes nature as its supplementary is strongly found guilty by Eco-criticism. During their banishment in forest, the Pandavas thoughtlessly used forest resources for their survival. In the novel, Draupadi relates how Nakul and Sahadev brought fawns for her to pet. They did not feel repentant to separate a new born from its mother, thereby reflecting their anthropocentric attitude. Nature brings the ideas of freedom from the constraints of life. Draupadi often dislikes her existence within the concrete palace walls of Kampilya and Hastinapur. She wants to escape to a world of flowers, trees and birds for her company. Even when Dussasan tries to unclothe her after her husbands, the Pandavas lost her in the dice game, she thinks of Krishna and finds herself in a tranquil garden.

Nature is a healer of pain as well as a residence of freedom. Draupadi after witnessing the devastations of cruel war, the horrible ends of her loved ones as well as her foes learns to let go of her ego. She no longer tries to govern over affairs but discusses things with her elders, even with Kunti whom she has disliked intensely ever since she gets married to her sons. Thus, this transformation is obvious in her attitude towards nature for she no longer tries to domesticate neither men nor nature. Additionally, the relationship of Bheeshma with Nature justifies a critical investigation in the novel. Bheeshma is the son of the river-goddess, Ganga, so a cherished relationship between him and Nature is perfectly suggested. The depressions and reluctances resulting from the court affairs and chiefly the enmity between the Kauravas and Pandavas often led him to find peace and

comfort in Nature. Divakaruni's retelling of the epic raises serious trepidations about environment. The author seems to give emphasis to the root of the problems of man and environment, the human ego. She attempts to bring out the issues of environment as voiced and treated as a serious issue in this novel.

Thus, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's both the selected novels are filled with the diverse facets and the elements of nature and its preordained role in the life of the people and in the Indian Myths.

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